

39 ongoing subduction of the Indian plate beneath the Eurasian plate along their west
40 boundary.

41 **Keywords: Afghanistan earthquake; InSAR; rainfall triggering; Coulomb**
42 **Stress; geodetic modeling**

43

44 **Introduction**

45 Based on rapid seismic report from U.S Geological Survey (USGS), a damaging Mw
46 6.0 earthquake struck eastern Afghanistan at 1:24 am local time (20:54 on June 21,
47 UTC). The reported hypocenter was located at a depth of ~10 km in the province of
48 Paktika, about 46 km southwest of Khōst, which lies close to the country's southern
49 border with Pakistan. The maximum intensity of the earthquake given by USGS was
50 estimated as VIII (Severe) in the epicentral area (Figure 1). More than 1,700 people
51 were killed, over 3,500 were injured (Rao *et al.*, 2022) and at least 10,000 homes were
52 destroyed by the earthquake accompanying a series of local landslides and fall rocks
53 (Figure 1), which makes this earthquake deadliest in decades for the region, according
54 to local news from Cable News Network (CNN). Its moment magnitude was later
55 modified to Mw 6.2 based on the USGS finite fault solution. Why this earthquake was
56 so destructive in spite of its moderate magnitude remains unanswered. This study
57 applies geodetic observations and regional rainfall data to explore the potential fault
58 and triggering mechanisms of this event.

59 Eastern Afghanistan lies at the southern edge of the Eurasian plate and next to the
60 western end of the Himalayan tectonic belt, which is being squeezed due to the motion
61 of the Indian plate from the southeast (Figure 1). Controlled by the regional orogenic
62 processes, the structures in this area are complex, where both thrust and strike-slip
63 faulting processes dominate the local tectonic deformation activities (Shnizai, 2020).
64 To the south, the Sulaiman Range was formed as the result of the crust counter-
65 clockwise rotation as the Indian plate moved northward, developing a complex fold-
66 thrust belt. Regional faulting behaviors include strike-slip, reverse-slip, and oblique-
67 slip movements that often led to previous shallow destructive earthquakes (Ambraseys
68 and Bilham, 2003; Shnizai, 2020). Among them, the left-lateral strike-slip Chaman fault
69 is the major tectonic boundary between the Eurasian and Indian plates with a slip rate
70 of 9-12 mm/y (Barnhart, 2016) (Figure 1), interacting with the Herat fault near Kabul
71 to the north (Prevot *et al.*, 1980; Ambraseys and Bilham, 2003; Shnizai, 2020).
72 Destructive earthquakes in 1505 (M_w 7.2), 1892 (M_w 6.5) and 1935 (M_w 7.7),
73 respectively, have been thought due to repeat activities of the Chaman fault (Ambraseys
74 and Bilham, 2003; Barnhart, 2016; Shnizai, 2020). To the north (Figure 1), north-
75 eastern Afghanistan reaches to the western Himalaya syntaxis, where the crust
76 deformed dramatically in response to the convergence of the Eurasian and the Indian
77 plates in the west since ~50 Ma ago (Molnar and Tapponnier, 1975), creating the Pamir-

78 Hindu Kush Mountain range. Intriguingly, the 2022 Afghanistan earthquake occurred
 79 in the interior of the Eurasian plate, and did not extend along those tectonic boundaries.

80 The area is highly seismically active due to the ongoing residual subduction of the
 81 lithosphere (the inset of Figure 1), primarily at depths of 70-200 km (Ambraseys and
 82 Bilham, 2003; Shnizai, 2020). An M_w 7.5 deep earthquake with the centroid depth of
 83 231 km struck the region in 2015, which was the largest event observed in the last two
 84 decades within a radius of 300 km around the 2022 event. There have also been two
 85 $M_w > 6$ and more than ten $M_w > 5$ historical earthquakes within 100 km of the event
 86 before the 2022 earthquake (Ambraseys and Bilham, 2003). Whether the regional
 87 seismicity, particularly the largest deep earthquake could exert positive effects on the
 88 2022 mainshock is not clear either, which requires additional work to clarify.

89 So far, it is highly demanded to further constrain the source parameters of the
 90 mainshock. Due to sparse local seismic network, the source parameters of the
 91 mainshock have not been well constrained. Significant differences of the fault
 92 parameters given by USGS and global CMT (GCMT) can be found in Table 2, in which
 93 the dip of the earthquake fault ranges from 57° to 87° . C-band Sentinel-1 (S1) A/B
 94 satellites launched by ESA regularly scan the earth surface in Terrain Observation with
 95 Progressive Scans (TOPS) imaging mode. In most tectonically active areas, the S1
 96 mission has 12 days revisit time, which makes TOPS SAR available to independently
 97 map the surface coseismic displacements of the 2022 Afghanistan earthquake.

98
 99 Figure 1. (a) Tectonic background of the 2022 M_w 6.3 Afghanistan earthquake and SAR spatial
 100 coverage. The green dots represent the historical earthquakes from 734 to 2002 obtained from
 101 Ambraseys & Bilham (2003), and the yellow dots represent the historical earthquakes from 1976 to
 102 2015 obtained from the USGS website (<http://earthquake.usgs.gov>, latest updated on 28 August,
 103 2022). The Shakesmap Modified Mercalli Intensity (MMI) Contours of the 2022 M_w 6.0 Afghanistan
 104 earthquake is released by USGS, while the faults data are from GRE Global Active Faults Database
 105 (GEM GAF-DB, <https://github.com/GEMScienceTools/gem-global-active-faults/>).

106 show coverage of Sentinel-1A data (ascending track T71 and descending track T78). The insert
 107 figure on the top right shows the Moho depths in the region based on CRUST1.0 (Laske *et al.*, 2013).
 108 (b) Collapsed roof of a mud house in Ermikhil village (Gayan). (c) Rock fall found in the Darazi
 109 village (Barmal). (d) Surface fractures observed in the Mastoon village (Gayan), at [69.4308E,
 110 32.9858], which is shown as *Site o* in Figure 2(a),

111 In this study, we conduct an InSAR analysis using TOPS SAR data collected by the
 112 Sentinel-1A satellite to constrain the surface coseismic deformation of the 2022 Mw 6.0
 113 Afghanistan earthquake and to compute fault geometry and slip distribution through
 114 geodetic modeling. We then discuss the possibility that the earthquake could have been
 115 triggered by the recent largest deep earthquake. Meanwhile, we also perform the
 116 meteorological data analysis to examine potential links between the rainfall and the
 117 mainshock. Based on the above results, we attempt to answer why this event caused so
 118 much damage.

119 InSAR deformation field

120 SAR data

121 SAR images used in this study are from the ESA’s Sentinel-1A satellite operating at C-
 122 band, with the wavelength of 5.54 cm. SAR images were acquired in the TOPS mode
 123 on two tracks, T78 (descending) and T71 (ascending), respectively, spanning nearly
 124 three months before and after the Afghanistan earthquake (Table 1). Regular global
 125 SAR acquisition allows us to have coseismic interferograms with short temporal
 126 baselines. However, as shown in Figure 2, unexpected fluctuations of the LOS
 127 measurements in the latest T71 and T78 coseismic pairs with the first post-earthquake
 128 SAR data can be observed 25 km west of the earthquake (Fig 2e), which is unlikely to
 129 result from the coseismic processes. Through extensive comparison, we finally select
 130 the SAR data as listed in Table 1 to obtain relatively clean coseismic deformation
 131 signals. We discuss the potential mechanisms responsible for those unexpected signals
 132 in discarded coseismic InSAR pairs in Section 4.

133

134 **Table 1. The selected interferometric pairs from Sentinel-1 SAR data used for the**
 135 **earthquake deformation analysis**

Track	Flight direction	Primary	Secondary	Inc*	Azi*	Modeling
T71	Ascending	20220419	20220724	36.6	-10.5	Yes
		20220618	20220630	36.6	-10.5	No
T78	Descending	20220502	20220725	37.7	-169.5	Yes
		20220619	20220701	37.7	-169.5	No

136 Note: *, Inc means incidence degree, and Azi is the azimuth angle of the flight relative to the north
 137 in the clockwise direction.

138 InSAR processing and coseismic deformation

139 Based on an automated processing environment *pSAR* (Feng *et al.*, 2016), the
140 GMTSAR software (Sandwell *et al.*, 2011; Xu *et al.*, 2018) has been ingested as the
141 InSAR processing kernel to carry out InSAR processing of TOPS SAR data. In the
142 processing, the 30-m resolution SRTM DEM data are used to eliminate the influence of
143 topography in the interferometric phase. The multi-looking numbers 2 and 8 in azimuth
144 and range directions are selected, while Gaussian and Goldstein (Goldstein and Werner,
145 1998) smoothing methods are successively applied to reduce the noise level of the
146 interferograms. The coherence threshold of 0.15 is set as the unwrapping threshold, and
147 the pixels below this value are filled with zeros before unwrapping. The Statistical-cost,
148 Network-flow Algorithm *Snaphu* is applied for two-dimensional phase unwrapping
149 (Chen and Zebker, 2001).

150 We use the GACOS and ERA5 external atmospheric data, respectively to estimate and
151 remove the atmospheric noise (Yu *et al.*, 2018; Y. Wang *et al.*, 2021). The results show
152 that the both methods produce almost identical results, significantly suppressing
153 topography-correlated signals in the selected coseismic interferograms. In order to
154 remove the potential orbital errors, we mask the core deformation area of the earthquake
155 in the geocoded unwrapped results, and then remove a plane estimated using the linear
156 least squares method from the data (Biggs *et al.*, 2007).

157 After these corrections, the coseismic deformation patterns can be clearly observed
158 (Figure 2). The coseismic deformation fringes of the 2022 Afghanistan earthquake are
159 continuous and clear, showing four-quadrant characteristics in the both tracks (Figures
160 2a and 2c), in which the T71 interferogram has four deformation centers with the
161 maximum LOS displacement of 39 cm (Figure 5a). The T78 pair exhibits more complex
162 deformation patterns with six deformation centers and the maximum displacement of
163 only 10 cm (Figure 5d). Significant difference of the two InSAR results in the ascending
164 and descending orbits indicates that the coseismic deformation is dominated by the
165 horizontal motion, which helps qualitatively identify the mechanism of the earthquake
166 as a strike-slip faulting process.
167

168

169 Figure 2. (a) T71 interferogram of 2022/04/17-2022/07/24. Surface fractures are found at site o as
 170 shown in Figure 1(c). (b) as (a) but produced with SAR data of 2022/06/18 and 2022/06/30. (c) T78
 171 interferogram of 2022/05/02-2022/07/25. (d) of another T78 coseismic pair with SAR data of
 172 2022/06/19 and 2022/07/01, which has shorted temporal baseline in T78. (e) InSAR LOS
 173 deformation along the AA' profile overlain on the topography. Note that all interferograms (a-d) are
 174 rewrapped with a range of -3 and 3 cm. The line of AA' is a profile crossing the deformation area of
 175 the earthquake.

176 InSAR modeling

177 We conduct a two-step inversion strategy to estimate fault geometric parameters and
 178 slip distributions of the earthquake based on the selected InSAR results using a geodetic
 179 inversion package, PSOKINV (Feng *et al.*, 2010, 2013, 2017). An elastic half-space
 180 dislocation Okada model is used in the forward simulation for the theoretical
 181 displacement field (Okada, 1985). To speed up the calculation and suppress the
 182 influence of the spatially correlated noise, we first downsample the coseismic
 183 interferograms with a quadtree algorithm to obtain a limited number of reference points
 184 for inversion (Simons *et al.*, 2002). Finally, 10203 and 16937 sampling points are
 185 obtained from T71 and T78, respectively.

186 **Nonlinear inversion of fault geometric parameters**

187 In the nonlinear stage, a hybrid global nonlinear particle swarm optimization algorithm
 188 (MPSO) is used to automatically determine the geometric parameters of the fault, e.g.
 189 strike, dip, depth, width and length. Based on the spatial coverages of the InSAR data,
 190 we set up reasonable searching boundaries for spatial locations of the fault. Meanwhile,
 191 a range from 0° to 359° is used for the strike, and a range from 10° to 89° is used for the
 192 dip. Usually, a narrow search range can dramatically increase the convergence rate in
 193 the inversion. The seismic solutions from either USGS or GCMT can be adapted to
 194 narrow down the search windows. The global nonlinear search finally obtains an
 195 optimal fitting solution for the Afghanistan earthquake (Table 2) in the sense of the least
 196 squares. The inversion results show that the centroid of the 2022 Mw 6.0 Afghanistan
 197 earthquake fault is located at [69.461° E, 32.993° N], and the fault plane is about 6.8
 198 km long and 7.9 km wide. The strike of 203.7° is in good agreement with the orientation
 199 of the local surface fractures observed in the field (Figure 1c), which is also close to
 200 one nodal plane of the seismic solutions from USGS and GCMT (Table 2). The rake
 201 angle of 6.9° implies an almost pure right-lateral strike-slip faulting for the earthquake.

202

203 **Table 2. Source parameters of the 2022 Mw 6.0 Afghanistan earthquake**

Source	Lon (°)	Lat (°)	Depth(km)*	L(km)	W(km)	Strike (°)	Dip (°)	Rake (°)	Mw
USGS	69.464	33.020	4.0	-	-	204	87	-11.0	6.0
GCMT	69.51	32.94	15.1	-	-	202	57	10	6.2
this study (uniform)	69.461	32.993	2.5	6.8	7.9	203.7	69.75	6.9	6.31
this study (variable)	69.461	32.993	-	20	12	203.7	68	6.9	6.32

204

205 **Distributed slip inversion**

206 In order to understand the details of the slip distribution of the earthquake, we further
 207 carry out a distributed slip inversion. Firstly, the fault is fixed based on the fault
 208 geometric parameters and location retrieved in the previous stage. Meanwhile, the
 209 length and width of the fault plane are extended to 20 km and 12 km, respectively. Then
 210 the fault plane is discretized into smaller fault units with a depth-dependent strategy
 211 (Fialko, 2004), which allows fine patch-sizes at shallow depths and coarse ones at depth.
 212 A total of 920 subfaults are obtained with a depth-dependent damping factor of 1.2. A
 213 range of rake angles [-25°, 25°] is applied to allow more freedom to explore the potential
 214 slip along the dip.

215 Once the fault location and geometric parameters are fixed, coseismic surface

216 displacements linearly vary with fault slips as $Gs = D$, where G is the Green's matrix
217 representing the theoretical surface deformation in response to unit slipping vectors on
218 individual subfaults, which is calculated based on the Okada elastic dislocation (Okada,
219 1985), D is the InSAR LOS observations, and s is the amount of slip to be solved
220 including two slip components along the two rake directions as defined. A second-order
221 Laplacian operator L is also applied in G to balance the trade-off between the data
222 misfits and the slip model roughness. Finally, the conjugate gradient method (Ward and
223 Barrientos, 1986) is used to solve the above linear equation for the coseismic slip
224 vectors s .

225 Under the assumption of a uniform slip, the dip angle is usually the most difficult
226 parameter to determine uniquely in the nonlinear inversion stage (Bürgmann *et al.*,
227 2002; Fukahata and Wright, 2008). To obtain an optimal dip angle, we apply an iterative
228 approach with a Log-function proposed by Feng *et al.* (2013) in the linear slip inversion
229 step to further refine the dip angle, in which we conduct a series of linear slip inversion
230 with variable dip angles to explore a global minimum solution. It is not necessary for
231 the global minimum from the Log-function method to overwhelm any other potentials
232 in the least squares sense, but a useful method to automatically return an acceptable
233 result. A unique global minimum derived from the Log-function is returned with an
234 optimal dip of 68° in this study (Figure 3).

235 To examine the performance of the seismic solutions of USGS and GCMT (Table 2),
236 we set up forward simulations with dip angles of 87° and 57° , respectively. The
237 residuals are evidently much larger than that derived from the optimal dip of 68°
238 estimated in this study, which can be found in the supporting document. Regarding the
239 variations of the dip angles provided from different institutes (Table 2), it may be due
240 to a curved complex fault of the 2022 earthquake, and the seismic results only reflect
241 different fault segments based on the seismic data of different frequencies used in their
242 individual seismic analysis. Since the InSAR observations are so far nearest to the
243 source in space, we believe our inversion result is solid enough to reflect the fault
244 segment of the major seismic energy.

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Figure 3. Contour map of Log-function under variable dips and smoothing strengths. White triangle indicates the optimal parameters with the global minimum.

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The coseismic slip distribution of the Afghanistan earthquake (Figure 4) shows that the slip ranges at depths of 1-9 km, in which the peak slip of about 3 m in the coseismic slip model appears at a depth of 2.5 km (Figure 4a). The main energy distribution of the fault model is concentrated within a 10 km long segment (Figure 4b) along the strike (relative to the epicenter) above 7 km (Figure 4c). Based on the distributed slip model (Figure 4), the total geodetic moment in the Afghanistan earthquake is 3.39×10^{18} Nm, equal to a moment magnitude of 6.32, which is slightly higher than estimated by USGS and GCMT (Table 2). Considering that the SAR data picked for the coseismic interferograms in this study cover more than one month after the mainshock, the slip model should contain a certain contribution of the early postseismic slip.

260

261 Figure 4. (a) Slip distribution of the 2022 Afghanistan earthquake from InSAR observations. The
 262 red star represents the initial motion point determined by USGS. (b) The green area shows the sum
 263 of scalar moment along depth and the red line shows the normalized slip as the function of the strike.
 264 (c) The gray area shows the sum of scalar moment along strike and the black line shows the
 265 normalized slip as the function of the depth.

266

267 Figure 5 shows that the optimal fault slip model determined in this paper can nicely
 268 reproduce the InSAR observations for both T78 and T71 interferograms. The coseismic
 269 interferometric fringe patterns and magnitudes have all been recovered based on the
 270 estimated slip model in this study. The significant residuals can only be found along the
 271 fault trace (Figures 5c and 5f), where the local non-elastic deformation and complex
 272 faulting segmentation may occur as observed in other previous studies (Feng and
 273 Almeida, 2020).

274

275 Figure 5. Comparison of the observed, predicted interferograms and their residuals. (a) Original
 276 InSAR observations of T71; (b) Predicted results of T71 based on the optimal slip model;
 277 (c) Residuals observed and simulated by T71 InSAR; (d, e, f) are the corresponding results of the
 278 T78 coseismic interferogram.

279

280 Discussion

281 Did Rainfall trigger the 2022 Mw 6.3 Afghanistan earthquake?

282 Fluid has long been known to play an important role in the occurrence of earthquakes
 283 (Cornet et al., 1997; Ellsworth, 2013; Ross et al., 2014; Weingarten et al., 2015), in
 284 which the subsurface fluid injection may directly activate the seismic fault slip
 285 (Bhattacharya and Viesca, 2019). A strong correlation between seasonal heavy rainfall
 286 or groundwater recharge and natural seismic activity has also been observed previously
 287 (Muço, 1999; Jiménez and García-Fernández, 2000; Ogasawara et al., 2002; Saar and
 288 Manga, 2003; Hainzl et al., 2006; Miller, 2008). Whether rainfall can trigger
 289 earthquakes remains unclear yet.

290 To further analyze the potential triggering mechanism of rainfall for the Afghanistan
 291 earthquake, we derive the rainfall data from Integrated Multi-satellitE Retrievals for
 292 GPM (IMERG), and Global Satellite Mapping of Precipitation (GSMaP). IMERG and
 293 GSMaP share the same data sources, whereas they use different algorithms. These two
 294 products are both generated from GPM Core Observatory (a dual-frequency

295 precipitation radar and a conical-scanning multichannel GPM Microwave Imager),
 296 other microwave constellation and infrared estimates from the US Geostationary
 297 Operational Environmental Satellite. IMERG (Huffman *et al.*, 2017) has three types
 298 products, namely early run, late run, and final run. The IMERG-early run adopts the
 299 forward direction of the morphing technique, and the IMERG-late run adds the
 300 backward morphing on top of the early run. The IMERG-final run is generated based
 301 on gauge adjustments. Since the final run is not available for the study period yet, we
 302 use IMERG-late run for the rainfall analysis. GSMaP further adds a Kalman filter
 303 method based on the two-way (forward and backward) morphing technique, producing
 304 the product of the GSMaP moving vector with Kalman filter (GSMaP-MVK). The
 305 GSMaP-gauge steps forward by gauge calibrations (Kubota *et al.*, 2006) based on the
 306 GSMaP-MVK, which is used in this study.

307 Obviously, the epicenter of the June 2022 earthquake falls in the maximum accumulated
 308 rainfall area based on the IMERG 30-minute precipitation data with up to 100 mm
 309 (Figure 6a). In time, the occurrence of the mainshock is observed 10 to 12 hours later
 310 after the occurrence of the largest rainfall rate at 10 mm per hour (Figure 6b).

311
 312 Figure 6. (a) Spatial distribution of accumulated rainfall on the day of the earthquake in
 313 Afghanistan, which is accumulated from the 30-minute IMERG-late run data. (b) Rainfall time
 314 series of nearly three days before and after the earthquake. Time zero represents the coseismic
 315 moment. The time series is generated by averaging rainfall within the circular centered on the

316 earthquake site with a radius of 25 km based on the 0.1°x0.1° resolution data (both IMERG and
317 GSMaP).

318

319 A widely accepted mechanism for rain-triggered earthquakes is that rainfall can result
320 in either pore fluid pressure variation in the elastic crustal media, or reduction of fault
321 friction coefficient (Hainzl *et al.*, 2006; Diao and Espinosa-marzal, 2018). The increase
322 of pore fluid pressure near the fault can reduce the effective normal stress, thereby
323 reducing the strength of the fault and promoting earthquake ruptures (Terakawa *et al.*,
324 2012; Jha and Juanes, 2014). According to our previous modeling results, the coseismic
325 rupture of the 2022 Afghanistan earthquake is very shallow with the maximum slip at
326 the 2.5 km depth. Thus, it is likely that the rainfall water could have penetrated to the
327 depth of the earthquake nucleation zone before the earthquake, where the pore pressure
328 of the crust was therefore increased favorable for the mainshock nucleating. The fact
329 that the mainshock may have been delayed triggering in response to the local rainfall
330 water processes has also been observed in the previous studies (Ogasawara *et al.*, 2002;
331 Saar and Manga, 2003), which can explain why the Afghanistan event occurred
332 approximately 10 hours later after the peak of the local rainfall (Figure 6b). In
333 conclusion, based on the strong correlation between the mainshock and local
334 precipitation in time and space, we speculate that the 2022 Afghanistan earthquake may
335 have been triggered by the rainfall. There may have another possibility that the rainfall
336 triggered shallow foreshocks which further triggered the mainshock. It will be helpful in
337 the future to combine the local well data and the early seismic data for an in-deep
338 investigation for this point.

339 In addition, the complex fringe patterns in the closest Sentinel-1 interferometric pairs
340 to the mainshock may also be explained by the rainfall water processes (Figure 2b
341 and 2d). During the rainfall processes, the soil moisture should have been significantly
342 changed relative to the earlier time, which then further affected the reflectivity of SAR
343 rays. Meanwhile, the rapid rainwater penetration could also induce a certain shallow
344 pore-elastic deformation. These may be the reasons why the InSAR signals formed with
345 the SAR data close to the mainshock in time are too complex to be true for the coseismic
346 displacements although they have been applied for coseismic analysis in Khac *et al.*
347 (2022). As shown in Figures 2a and 2c, the coseismic interferograms with the picked
348 SAR data away from the mainshock can clearly present the coseismic deformation
349 fringes after a simple topography-correlated APS correction (Figure 2).

350

351 **Why did the moderate earthquake cause lots of damages?**

352 The 2022 M_w 6.3 Afghanistan earthquake is the deadliest event in Afghanistan in last
353 two decades, but not largest in magnitude. Compared to other seven M_w 5.9-6.9
354 earthquakes (Table 3), the maximum slip of the 2022 Afghanistan event is significantly
355 larger than the others, including the 2003 M_w 6.5 Bam earthquake (Table 3). Relatively,
356 the 2022 Afghanistan earthquake lasted approximately 15 s with the peak duration

357 during the first 5 s, which is shorter than the others. Previous studies have suggested
 358 that the moment corner frequency is proportional inversely to the duration of the
 359 coseismic rupture processes (Chen and Abercrombie, 2020). As the stress drop $\Delta\sigma$ of
 360 an earthquake is proportional to its corner frequency (Eshelby and Peierls, 1957), it is
 361 given as

$$362 \quad \Delta\sigma = \frac{7M_0}{16} \frac{f_c^3}{(k\beta)^3} \quad (1)$$

363 where M_0 is the seismic moment of the event, k and β are constants related to
 364 rupture dimension. Thus, the stress drop of the 2022 mainshock turns to be higher than
 365 expected regarding its magnitude (Table 3). As the stress drop is highly correlated to
 366 the local ground motion (Oth *et al.*, 2017), the short duration of the earthquake rupture
 367 is the key factor to accelerate the local ground motion, which is further responsible for
 368 the building damages in addition to the effects of its shallow rupture processes.

369 Moreover, as observed in the fields in Figure 1(b, c and d), the 2022 earthquake fault
 370 just extended under the local villages and the mainshock took place at local time 1:24
 371 a.m., when most people were sleeping indoors. Meanwhile, many home buildings were
 372 especially vulnerable as they were mostly made of mud and other natural materials,
 373 contributing to the high number of casualties. All these factors finally resulted in the
 374 deadly effects from the earthquake.

375

376 **Table 3. Maximum slip data of some M_w 5.9-6.9 earthquakes**

Event	M_w	Dep(km)	Maximum of slip (m)	Duration(s)	Sources
2003 Bam earthquake	6.5	10.0	2.7	11(5)	(Wang <i>et al.</i> , 2004; Poiata <i>et al.</i> , 2012)
2008 Gaize earthquake	6.4 (F1)	10.0	1.9	-	(Feng <i>et al.</i> , 2009)
	5.9 (F2)	9.0	1.0	-	(Feng <i>et al.</i> , 2009)
2008 Damxung earthquake	6.3	12.0	~2.0	10	(Feng <i>et al.</i> , 2010; Gao <i>et al.</i> , 2010)
2010 Yushu earthquake	6.9	14.0	~1.5	16(8)	(Zhang <i>et al.</i> , 2010; Li <i>et al.</i> , 2011)
2020 Yutian earthquake	6.25	10.0	0.9	12	(Feng <i>et al.</i> , 2022)
2021 Yangbi earthquake	6.07	9.0	~0.8	9.1	(S. Wang <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
2022 Afghanistan earthquake	6.32	2.5	~3	15(5) *	This study

377 Note: * means the major rupture lasted about 5 s in the total rupture duration of 15 s in
 378 the 2022 earthquake, which is derived from USGS.

379 **The effect of the 2015 Hindu Kush M_w 7.5 earthquake**

380 After the occurrence of a large earthquake, the local crustal stress is disturbed, which
381 may reactivate nearby faults (King and Cocco, 2001; Freed, 2005). In 2015, an M_w 7.5
382 earthquake occurred in the Hindu Kush region at a depth of about 231 km (USGS),
383 nearly 400 km north of the epicenter of the 2022 M_w 6.0 Afghanistan earthquake. The
384 2015 Hindu Kush earthquake is the closest major earthquake in time and space to the
385 2022 event (Figure 1). Here we attempt to analyze the potential triggering effect of the
386 2015 deep Hindu Kush earthquake on the 2022 shallow Afghanistan earthquake. Using
387 the 2022 earthquake fault as the received fault (Table 2), we calculate co- and post-
388 seismic triggering stress of the 2015 earthquake using PSGRN/PSCMP codes (Wang *et al.*,
389 *et al.*, 2006). Due to the lack of knowledge of the rheological structure of the lithosphere,
390 we treat the Moho depth of the study area as the thickness of the elastic layer based on
391 the CRUST1.0 models, below which is the viscoelastic layer with the postseismic
392 viscoelastic response. Considering that the main rupture area of the 2015 deep
393 earthquake was ~ 231 km below the surface, we set up the local lithospheric
394 stratification structure in the calculation based on the Preliminary Reference Earth
395 Model (PREM) (Dziewonski and Anderson, 1981). A range of viscosities from 10^{17} and
396 10^{21} Pas based on the recent studies (Clark and Royden, 2000; Huang *et al.*, 2014;
397 Bischoff and Flesch, 2018, 2019) is successively taken for the upper and lower limits
398 of the local viscoelastic layer in the calculation.

399 According to the fault slip depth obtained by our inversion (Figure 4), the co- and post-
400 seismic Coulomb failure stress (CFS) maps at depths of [0,2.5,5,10] km are created.
401 Figure 7 shows the results of the Coulomb stress changes (CSC) at a depth of 2.5 km
402 caused by the 2015 deep earthquake. In fact, the results at all depths present similar
403 patterns (Figures S3 - S9), suggesting that the coseismic Coulomb stress triggered by
404 the 2015 Hindu Kush earthquake is positive on the 2022 Afghanistan earthquake.
405 However, in the consideration of potential viscoelastic rebounds, the postseismic
406 viscoelastic Coulomb stress variation after 7 years turns to be negative with CFS
407 magnitude of < 0.001 MPa. The results show that the coseismic process of the 2015
408 deep earthquake caused a shear load near the 2022 shallow earthquake, but the
409 influence of the postseismic viscoelastic deformation process is very limited. This
410 means that the 2015 deep earthquake had slight effects on the wide area in southern
411 Afghanistan. Hence, the earthquake disaster in Afghanistan may potentially be
412 controlled by the impact of the collision between the Eurasian and Indian plates from
413 the northeast boundary.

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Figure 7. Coulomb stress changes caused by the 2015 M_w 7.5 Hindu Kush earthquake at a depth of 2.5 km with a viscosity of 10^{17} Pa s. (a) The coseismic CSC; (b) The postseismic viscoelastic Δ CFS in the first 6.66 years (October 26, 2015-June 21, 2022). The white rectangles are the projection of the all subfaults on the surface.

420 Conclusion

421 In this paper, we obtained the coseismic deformation fields of the 2022 M_w 6.3
422 Afghanistan earthquake using Sentinel-1 TOPS interferometry, and then determined the
423 source parameters and coseismic slip distribution. With these preliminary results, we
424 come to the following conclusions:

- 425 1. The optimal coseismic fault geometry shows that the earthquake fault has a strike
426 of 203.7° , a dip of 68° and a rake of 6.9° . The coseismic slip of the mainshock is
427 concentrated mainly in the range of 1.5-10 km underground with the maximum slip
428 ~ 3 m at a depth of 2.5 km. The moment magnitude of the earthquake is M_w 6.32,
429 and the epicenter (centroid of the fault) is located at [69.461° E, 32.993° N].
- 430 2. Heavy monsoon rains hit Afghanistan before and after the earthquake. The rainfall
431 has a strong correlation with the earthquake occurrence in time and space, which
432 implies that the earthquake sequence may be triggered by rainfall. In addition, the
433 local rainfall has a great influence on the interferometric signal patterns of the
434 interferograms from those SAR acquisitions close to the mainshock, so it is
435 necessary to select the appropriate interferometric pairs carefully for modeling in
436 this case.

- 437 3. The Afghanistan earthquake caused huge casualties and damage in the local area,
438 which is mainly related to the characteristics of the source: (a) the depth of the
439 earthquake is very shallow; (b) the maximum slip reaches ~3 m, which exceeds
440 other earthquakes at the similar magnitudes; (c) the coseismic slip distribution is
441 concentrated in a narrow area, and the coseismic stress drop is high.
- 442 4. The 2015 Mw 7.5 Hindu Kush deep earthquake has a certain effect on the 2022
443 Afghanistan earthquake, particularly due to its coseismic rupture.
- 444

445 **Data and Resources**

446 The Sentinel-1 data used in this study were downloaded from the ESA Sentinels data
447 hub (<https://scihub.copernicus.eu/>). The interferograms were generated using the open
448 source InSAR package, GMTSAR(<https://topex.ucsd.edu/gmtsar/>). The obtained slip
449 model of the 2022 Mw 6.3 Afghanistan earthquake in this study has been shared online
450 (https://zenodo.org/record/7246514#.Y1cyuLZBw_U). The slip model of the 2015
451 deep earthquake has also been re-shaped in a simple ASCII format, which can also be
452 found through the above link. The modeling and numerical analysis were conducted in
453 this study using a geodetic modeling package - PSOKINV, which is available upon
454 request.

455 **Declaration of Competing Interests**

456 The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest recorded.

457

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